

Fuzzy enriched contraction for α_L -fuzzy fixed point results in b-metric spaces satisfying L-fuzzy mappings with application

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Oral Presentation</p> <p>Doi : 10.5281/zenodo.14331936</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords</p> <p>α_L-fuzzy fixed point b-metric space common α_L-fuzzy fixed point L-fuzzy mappings multivalued mappings</p>	<p>The paper aims to introduce the notion of L-fuzzy mapping and establish α_L-fuzzy fixed point results for rational contraction in a complete b-metric spaces. These contributions extend the existing literature on fuzzy mappings and fixed point theory. Through illustrative examples, we showcase the practical applicability of our proposed results. Also, we explore as an application, the solution for fuzzy contraction to derive the existence of α_L-fuzzy fixed point results for multivalued mappings in b-metric spaces.</p>

1. Introduction

Numerous problems encountered in everyday life stem from incomplete information that is not well-expressed in conventional mathematics. In 1965, Zadeh [2] introduced the notion of fuzzy sets, that proffer efficient means to handle imprecise information, laying the foundation for subsequent research in fuzzy mathematics. Building upon Zadeh's work, Goguen [3] extended this concept of the fuzzy set to L-fuzzy set thereby replacing the interval [0, 1] by L that is a completely distributive lattice. Heilpern [4] further extended the notion of fuzzy mappings and derived fixed point results in the metric linear space. For more, we refer [1, 5, 7, 10, 11, 15]. Rashid et al. [6] introduced the conception of β_{FL} -admissible for two L-fuzzy mappings and derived numerous results for these mappings. Moreover, Alnaser et al. [16] used the concept of fuzzy mappings and proved some fixed point results in F-metric space with some open problems such as fixed point theorems for L-fuzzy mappings. In this direction, Lateef [18] introduced the notion of F-metric space as a generalization of traditional metric space and proved Banach contraction principle in the setting of this generalized metric space and establish some common fixed point theorems for (β - ψ)-contractions.

Recently, Kanwal et al. [12] introduced two fuzzy fixed point theorems of L-fuzzy mappings and proved for two contractive type conditions in b-metric spaces.

Based on the above insight, we introduce the concepts of L-fuzzy mapping and subsequently establish α_L -fuzzy fixed point results for rational contraction within the framework of

complete b-metric spaces. To bolster our findings, we offer illustrative examples demonstrating the practical application of the presented results. Also, we explore as an application, the solution for fuzzy contraction to derive the existence of α_L -fuzzy fixed point results for multivalued mappings in b-metric spaces.

2. Preliminaries

We begin this section by presenting the concept of L-fuzzy mapping and b-metric spaces.

Definition 2.1 [9,20] Let $L \neq \emptyset$ and \leq_L be partial order set and (L, \leq_L) be a partially ordered set.

(i) For any $x, y \in L, x \vee y \in L, x \wedge y \in L$, then L is referred to as lattice.

(ii) For any $\Omega \in L, \vee \Omega \in L, \wedge \Omega \in L$, then L referred to as complete lattice.

(iii) For any $x, y, z \in L, x \vee (y \wedge z) = (x \vee y) \wedge (x \vee z), x \wedge (y \vee z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z)$, then L is referred to as distributive lattice.

Definition 2.2 [8, 15, 13] Let L-fuzzy set Ω on a nonempty set X. A function $\Omega: X \rightarrow L$, where L satisfies (iii) of definition 2.1 with 1_L (top element) and 0_L (bottom element).

The α_L -level set of Ω is denoted by Ω_{α_L} define as

$$\Omega_{\alpha_L} = \{x: \alpha_L \leq_L \Omega(x)\} \text{ if } \alpha_L \in L \setminus \{0_L\},$$

$$\Omega_{0_L} = \{x: 0_L \leq_L \Omega(x)\}.$$

Then, $\mathcal{F}_L(X)$ and $\text{cl}(\Omega)$ denotes L-fuzzy set on X and closure of Ω .

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Define

$$X_{L_\wedge} = \begin{cases} 0_L, & \text{if } x \notin \Omega \\ 1_L, & \text{if } x \in \Omega, \end{cases}$$

The characteristic function X_{L_\wedge} of L -fuzzy set Ω .

We now, introduce b -metric space as follows:

Definition 2.3 [17] Let X be a nonempty set and $s \geq 1$ be a given real number. $d: X \times X \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is said to be b -metric if and only if, for all $x, y, z \in X$, the following conditions are satisfied:

- i. $d(x, y) = 0$ if and only if $x = y$;
- ii. $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$;
- iii. $d(x, z) \leq s[d(x, y) + d(y, z)]$.

A triplet (X, d, s) , is called a b -metric space.

Next is the example of b -metric space.

Example 2.4 [21] Consider $X = [0, 1]$, $d: X \times X \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ and defined $d(x, y) = (x - y)^2$,

for all $x, y \in X$. Clearly, $(X, d, 2)$ is a b -metric space.

Definition 2.5 [12] Let (X, d) be a b -metric space and $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in X . Then $\{x_n\}$ is said to be convergent sequence if there exists $x \in X$, such that for all $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $n_0(\varepsilon) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n \geq n_0(\varepsilon)$, we get

$$d(x_n, x) < \varepsilon.$$

Then, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$.

Definition 2.6 [12] Let (X, d) is a b -metric space and $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in X . Then $\{x_n\}$ is said to be Cauchy sequence if for all $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $n_0(\varepsilon) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n \geq n_0(\varepsilon)$, we get

$$d(x_n, x) < \varepsilon$$

Definition 2.7 [12] Let (X, d) is a b -metric space and $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in X . Then, X is said to be complete if every Cauchy sequence in X is convergent in X .

Definition 2.8 [15] Let (X, d) be a b -metric space. Hausdorff metric H on $CB(X)$ induced by d is defined as

$$H(A, B) = \max \left\{ \sup_{a \in A} d(a, B), \sup_{b \in B} d(A, b) \right\}$$

for all $A, B \in CB(X)$, where

$$d(a, B) = \inf \{d(a, b) : b \in B\}$$

Lemma 2.9 [21] Assume that A and B are bounded, nonempty subsets of a b -metric space (X, d) . If $a \in A$, then

$$d(a, B) \leq H(A, B)$$

Lemma 2.10 [21] Assume that A and B are bounded, nonempty subsets of a b -metric space (X, d) and $0 < \sigma \in \mathbb{R}$. Then for $a \in A$, there exists $b \in B$ such that

$$d(a, b) \leq H(A, B) + \sigma$$

Definition 2.11 An α_L -fuzzy fixed point of a fuzzy mapping $T: X \rightarrow F(X)$ is defined as a point $x^* \in X$ where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ and $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha(x^*)}$.

Definition 2.12 A common α_L -fuzzy fixed point of a fuzzy mappings $T, f: X \rightarrow F(X)$ is defined as a point $x^* \in X$ where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ and $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha(x^*)} \cap [fx^*]_{\alpha(x^*)}$.

3. Main Results

Theorem 3.1. Let X be nonempty set, d be a metric and (X, d) be complete b -metric space with constant $b \geq 1$. Let T be a L -fuzzy mapping from X into $\mathcal{F}_L(X)$ and for all $x, y \in X$, $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i < 1$ with $a_1 + 2ba_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_5 < 1$, there exists $\alpha_L(x), \alpha_L(y) \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$ such that

$[Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}$ and $[Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}$ are nonempty and belong to $CB(X)$ satisfying the requirement:

$$H([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) \leq a_1 d(x, y) + a_2 d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + a_3 d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) + a_4 \frac{d(x, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, y) + d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})} + a_5 \frac{d(x, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})} \quad (3.1)$$

Then, T has an α_L -fuzzy fixed point $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}$.

Proof Let us choose any arbitrary point $x_0 \in X$ and $[Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)} \neq 0$. Let $x_1 \in [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}$ and $x_2 \in [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}$

and so on. Since $[Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)} \neq 0$ and $[Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)} \neq 0$ are closed and bounded subsets of X and by using Lemma 2.10,

there exists $x_2 \in [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}$ such that

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq H([Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5),$$

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) + a_2 d(x_0, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + a_3 d(x_1, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_0, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)})d(x_1, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})}{d(x_0, x_1) + d(x_0, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + d(x_1, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)})} + a_5 \frac{d(x_0, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)})d(x_0, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + d(x_1, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)})d(x_1, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})}{d(x_0, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + d(x_1, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)})} + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)$$

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) + a_2 d(x_0, x_2) + a_3 d(x_1, x_1) + a_4 \frac{d(x_0, x_1)d(x_1, x_2)}{d(x_0, x_1) + d(x_0, x_2) + d(x_1, x_1)} + a_5 \frac{d(x_0, x_1)d(x_0, x_2) + d(x_1, x_1)d(x_1, x_2)}{d(x_0, x_2) + d(x_1, x_1)} + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)$$

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) + a_2 d(x_0, x_2) + a_3 d(x_1, x_1) + a_4 d(x_0, x_1) + a_5 d(x_0, x_1) + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)$$

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) + ba_2 d(x_0, x_1) + ba_2 d(x_1, x_2) + a_4 d(x_0, x_1) + a_5 d(x_0, x_1) + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)$$

$$(1 - ba_2)d(x_1, x_2) \leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) + ba_2 d(x_0, x_1) + a_4 d(x_0, x_1) + a_5 d(x_0, x_1) + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)$$

$$(1 - ba_2)d(x_1, x_2) \leq (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)d(x_0, x_1) + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)$$

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)}{(1 - ba_2)} d(x_0, x_1) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)}{(1 - ba_2)} \quad (3.2)$$

Set $\sigma = \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)}{(1 - ba_2)}$, then (3.2) becomes

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq \sigma d(x_0, x_1) + \sigma \quad (3.3)$$

Again, $[Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)} \neq 0$ is a closed and bounded subsets of X

and using Lemma 2.10, there exists $x_3 \in [Tx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}$ such that

$$d(x_2, x_3) \leq H([Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}, [Tx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)},$$

$$d(x_2, x_3) \leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) + a_2 d(x_1, [Tx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + a_3 d(x_2, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_1, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})d(x_2, [Tx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)})}{d(x_1, x_2) + d(x_1, [Tx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + d(x_2, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})} + a_5 \frac{d(x_1, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})d(x_1, [Tx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + d(x_2, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})d(x_2, [Tx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)})}{d(x_1, [Tx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + d(x_2, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})} + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)}$$

$$d(x_2, x_3) \leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) + a_2 d(x_1, x_3) + a_3 d(x_2, x_2) + a_4 \frac{d(x_1, x_2)d(x_1, x_3) + d(x_2, x_2)d(x_2, x_3)}{d(x_1, x_2) + d(x_1, x_3) + d(x_2, x_2)} + a_5 \frac{d(x_1, x_2)d(x_1, x_3) + d(x_2, x_2)d(x_2, x_3)}{d(x_1, x_3) + d(x_2, x_2)} + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)}$$

$$d(x_2, x_3) \leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) + a_2 d(x_1, x_3) + a_3 d(x_2, x_2) + a_4 d(x_1, x_2) + a_5 d(x_1, x_2) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x_2, x_3) &\leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) + ba_2 d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + ba_2 d(x_2, x_3) + a_4 d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + a_5 d(x_1, x_2) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)} \\
 (1 - ba_2) d(x_2, x_3) &\leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + ba_2 d(x_1, x_2) + a_4 d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + a_5 d(x_1, x_2) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)} \\
 (1 - ba_2) d(x_2, x_3) &\leq (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5) d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)} \\
 d(x_2, x_3) &\leq \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)}{(1 - ba_2)} d(x_1, x_2) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)^2} \quad (3.4)
 \end{aligned}$$

Set $\sigma^2 = \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)^2}$, then (3.4) becomes

$$d(x_2, x_3) \leq \sigma d(x_1, x_2) + \sigma^2 \quad (3.5)$$

Using (3.3) in (3.5), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x_2, x_3) &\leq \sigma[\sigma d(x_0, x_1) + \sigma] + \sigma^2 \\
 d(x_2, x_3) &\leq \sigma^2 d(x_0, x_1) + 2\sigma^2 \quad (3.6)
 \end{aligned}$$

Continuing in this manner, we create a sequence x_n of points in X such that $x_n \in [Tx_{n-1}]_{\alpha(x_{n-1})}$, we can choose $x_{n+1} \in [Tx_n]_{\alpha(x_n)}$ such that

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq \sigma^n d(x_0, x_1) + n\sigma^n. \quad (3.7)$$

Now, for positive integers n, m ($n > m$), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x_m, x_n) &\leq b[d(x_m, x_{m+1}) + d(x_{m+1}, x_{m+2}) + \dots + d(x_{n-1}, x_n)] \\
 d(x_m, x_n) &\leq b[\sigma^m d(x_0, x_1) + m\sigma^m + \sigma^{m+1} d(x_0, x_1) \\
 &\quad + (m + 1)\sigma^{m+1} + \dots + \sigma^{n-1} d(x_0, x_1) \\
 &\quad + (n - 1)\sigma^{n-1}] \\
 d(x_m, x_n) &\leq b \left[(\sigma^m + \sigma^{m+1} + \dots + \sigma^{n-1}) d(x_0, x_1) + \sum_{i=m}^{n-1} i\sigma^i \right]. \quad (3.8)
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $\sigma^m + \sigma^{m+1} + \dots + \sigma^{n-1}$ is a geometric series with $\sigma < 1$, hence convergent. So, from (3.8), we have

$$d(x_m, x_n) \leq b \left[\frac{\sigma^m}{1 - \sigma} d(x_0, x_1) + \sum_{i=m}^{n-1} i\sigma^i \right]. \quad (3.9)$$

On taking $m, n \rightarrow \infty$ and $\sigma < 1$, the series $\sum_{i=m}^{n-1} i\sigma^i$ converges by Cauchy root test, then

$$d(x_m, x_n) \rightarrow 0. \quad (3.10)$$

Hence existence of Cauchy sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X . Since X is complete, then there exist $x^* \in X$ such that $x_n \rightarrow x^*$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Now to show that x^* is an α_L -fuzzy fixed point, we consider

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n+1}, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})] \\
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + H([Tx_n]_{\alpha(x_n)}, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})] \\
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b \left[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_1 d(x_n, x^*) + a_2 d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \right. \\
 &\quad + a_3 d(x^*, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_n, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, x^*) + d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)})} \\
 &\quad \left. + a_5 \frac{d(x_n, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)}) d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)})} \right] \\
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b \left[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_1 d(x_n, x^*) + a_2 d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \right. \\
 &\quad + a_3 d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, x^*) + d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \\
 &\quad \left. + a_5 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1}) d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

implies

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b \left[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_1 d(x_n, x^*) + ba_2 d(x_n, x^*) + ba_2 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \right. \\
 &\quad + a_3 d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, x^*) + d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \\
 &\quad \left. + a_5 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1}) d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \right] \quad (3.11)
 \end{aligned}$$

On taking $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.11), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b[ba_2 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})] \\
 (1 - b(ba_2)) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq 0 \\
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq 0 \quad (3.12)
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $(1 - b(ba_2)) \neq 0$. Then $d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) = 0$.

Hence $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}$.

Example 3.2. Consider $X = [a, a + 1]$, for all $a \in \mathbb{R}$ and $d: X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is define $d(x, y) = |x - y|$. We define $T: X \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_L(X)$ as

$$T(x)(t) = \begin{cases} a + 1, & \text{if } a < t \leq \frac{x}{4} \\ \frac{a + 1}{2}, & \text{if } \frac{x}{4} < t \leq \frac{x}{3} \\ \frac{a + 1}{4}, & \text{if } \frac{x}{3} < t \leq \frac{x}{2} \\ a, & \text{if } \frac{x}{2} < t \leq a + 1. \end{cases}$$

For all $x, y \in X$ and $L = [a, a + 1]$, there exists $\alpha_L(x) = \alpha_L(y) = a + 1$, such that

$$[Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)} = \left[a, \frac{x}{4} \right]$$

and

$$[Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)} = \left[a, \frac{t}{4} \right].$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} H([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) &= \left| \frac{y}{4} - \frac{x}{4} \right|, \\ d(x, y) &= |x - y|, \\ d(x, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) &= \left| x - \frac{x}{4} \right|, \\ d(y, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) &= \left| y - \frac{y}{4} \right|, \\ d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) &= \left| x - \frac{y}{4} \right|, \\ d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) &= \left| y - \frac{x}{4} \right|. \end{aligned}$$

We obtain in (3.1) with $a_1 = \frac{1}{25}, a_2 = \frac{1}{15}, a_3 = \frac{1}{20}, a_4 = \frac{1}{5}, a_5 = \frac{1}{10}$

$$\begin{aligned} H([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) &\leq \frac{1}{25}|x - y| + \frac{1}{15}\left|x - \frac{y}{4}\right| + \frac{1}{20}\left|y - \frac{x}{4}\right| \\ &+ \frac{1}{5} \frac{\left|x - \frac{x}{4}\right| \left|y - \frac{y}{4}\right|}{|x - y| + \left|x - \frac{y}{4}\right| + \left|y - \frac{x}{4}\right|} \\ &+ \frac{1}{10} \frac{\left|x - \frac{x}{4}\right| \left|x - \frac{y}{4}\right| + \left|y - \frac{x}{4}\right| \left|y - \frac{y}{4}\right|}{\left|x - \frac{y}{4}\right| + \left|y - \frac{x}{4}\right|} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, all the conditions of Theorem 3.1 are satisfied with $a \in X$. Thus, there exists $a \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$, that is, $a \in [Ta]_{\alpha_L(a)}$.

Theorem 3.3. Let X be a nonempty set, d be a metric and (X, d) be complete b-metric space with constant $b \geq 1$. Let T, f be L-fuzzy mapping from X into $\mathcal{F}_L(X)$ and for all $x, y \in X$, $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i < 1$ with $a_1 + 2ba_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_5 < 1$, there exists $\alpha_L(x), \alpha_L(y) \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$ such that $[Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}$ or $[fx]_{\alpha_L(x)}$ and $[Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}$ or $[fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}$ are nonempty and belong to $CB(X)$ satisfying the following requirement:

$$\begin{aligned} H([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) &\leq a_1 d(x, y) + a_2 d(x, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + a_3 d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) \\ &+ a_4 \frac{d(x, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) d(y, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, y) + d(x, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})} \\ &+ a_5 \frac{d(x, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) d(x, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) d(y, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})} \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

Then, T and f have a common α_L -fuzzy fixed point $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)} \cap [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}$.

Proof Let us choose a point $x_0 \in X$, there exists $\alpha_L(x_0) \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$ such that $[Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}$ is nonempty and there exists a point $x_1 \in [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}$ or $x_1 \in [fx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}$. Again, for x_2 , there exists $\alpha_L(x_1) \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$ such that $[Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}$ and $[fx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)} \in CB(X)$.

With (3.13) and Lemma 2.10, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_1, x_2) &\leq \\ H([Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}, [fx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) &+ (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5), \\ d(x_1, x_2) &\leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) + a_2 d(x_0, [fx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + a_3 d(x_1, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}) \\ &+ a_4 \frac{d(x_0, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}) d(x_1, [fx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})}{d(x_0, x_1) + d(x_0, [fx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + d(x_1, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)})} \\ &+ a_5 \frac{d(x_0, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}) d(x_0, [fx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + d(x_1, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)}) d(x_1, [fx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})}{d(x_0, [fx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) + d(x_1, [Tx_0]_{\alpha_L(x_0)})} + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5) \\ d(x_1, x_2) &\leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) + a_2 d(x_0, x_2) + a_3 d(x_1, x_1) \\ &+ a_4 \frac{d(x_0, x_1) d(x_0, x_2) + d(x_1, x_1) d(x_1, x_2)}{d(x_0, x_1) + d(x_0, x_2) + d(x_1, x_1)} \\ &+ a_5 \frac{d(x_0, x_1) d(x_0, x_2) + d(x_1, x_1) d(x_1, x_2)}{d(x_0, x_2) + d(x_1, x_1)} + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_1, x_2) &\leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) + a_2 d(x_0, x_2) \\ &+ a_3 d(x_1, x_1) + a_4 d(x_0, x_1) + a_5 d(x_0, x_1) \\ &+ (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5) \\ d(x_1, x_2) &\leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) + ba_2 d(x_0, x_1) \\ &+ ba_2 d(x_1, x_2) + a_4 d(x_0, x_1) \\ &+ a_5 d(x_0, x_1) + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5) \\ (1 - ba_2) d(x_1, x_2) &\leq a_1 d(x_0, x_1) \\ &+ ba_2 d(x_0, x_1) + a_4 d(x_0, x_1) \\ &+ a_5 d(x_0, x_1) + (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5) \\ (1 - ba_2) d(x_1, x_2) &\leq (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5) d(x_0, x_1) \\ &+ (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5) \end{aligned}$$

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)}{(1 - ba_2)} d(x_0, x_1) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)}{(1 - ba_2)} \quad (3.14)$$

Set $\sigma = \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)}{(1 - ba_2)}$, then (3.14) becomes

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq \sigma d(x_0, x_1) + \sigma \quad (3.15)$$

Again, $[Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)} \neq 0$ is a closed and bounded subsets of X and using Lemma 2.10, there exists $x_3 \in [fx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_2, x_3) &\leq H([Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}, [fx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)}, \\ d(x_2, x_3) &\leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) + a_2 d(x_1, [fx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + a_3 d(x_2, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) \\ &+ a_4 \frac{d(x_1, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) d(x_2, [fx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)})}{d(x_1, x_2) + d(x_1, [fx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + d(x_2, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})} \\ &+ a_5 \frac{d(x_1, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) d(x_1, [fx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + d(x_2, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)}) d(x_2, [fx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)})}{d(x_1, [fx_2]_{\alpha_L(x_2)}) + d(x_2, [Tx_1]_{\alpha_L(x_1)})} + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)} \\ d(x_2, x_3) &\leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) + a_2 d(x_1, x_3) + a_3 d(x_2, x_2) \\ &+ a_4 \frac{d(x_1, x_2) d(x_2, x_3)}{d(x_1, x_2) + d(x_1, x_3) + d(x_2, x_2)} \\ &+ a_5 \frac{d(x_1, x_2) d(x_1, x_3) + d(x_2, x_2) d(x_2, x_3)}{d(x_1, x_3) + d(x_2, x_2)} + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_2, x_3) &\leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) + a_2 d(x_1, x_3) \\ &+ a_3 d(x_2, x_2) + a_4 d(x_1, x_2) + a_5 d(x_1, x_2) \\ &+ \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x_2, x_3) &\leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) + ba_2 d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + ba_2 d(x_2, x_3) + a_4 d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + a_5 d(x_1, x_2) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)} \\
 (1 - ba_2) d(x_2, x_3) &\leq a_1 d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + ba_2 d(x_1, x_2) + a_4 d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + a_5 d(x_1, x_2) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)} \\
 (1 - ba_2) d(x_2, x_3) &\leq (a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5) d(x_1, x_2) \\
 &\quad + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)} \\
 d(x_2, x_3) &\leq \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)}{(1 - ba_2)} d(x_1, x_2) + \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)^2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

Set $\sigma^2 = \frac{(a_1 + ba_2 + a_4 + a_5)^2}{(1 - ba_2)^2}$, then (3.17) becomes

$$d(x_2, x_3) \leq \sigma d(x_1, x_2) + \sigma^2 \tag{3.18}$$

Using (3.15) in (3.18), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x_2, x_3) &\leq \sigma[\sigma d(x_0, x_1) + \sigma] + \sigma^2 \\
 d(x_2, x_3) &\leq \sigma^2 d(x_0, x_1) + 2\sigma^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.19}$$

Again, continuing in this fashion, we create a sequence x_n of points in X such that $x_n \in [Tx_{n-1}]_{\alpha(x_{n-1})}$, we can choose $x_{n+1} \in [Tx_n]_{\alpha(x_n)}$ such that

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq \sigma^n d(x_0, x_1) + n\sigma^n. \tag{3.20}$$

For positive integers n, m ($n > m$), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x_m, x_n) &\leq b[d(x_m, x_{m+1}) + d(x_{m+1}, x_{m+2}) + \dots + d(x_{n-1}, x_n)] \\
 d(x_m, x_n) &\leq b[\sigma^m d(x_0, x_1) + m\sigma^m + \sigma^{m+1} d(x_0, x_1) + (m+1)\sigma^{m+1} + \dots \\
 &\quad + \sigma^{n-1} d(x_0, x_1) + (n-1)\sigma^{n-1}] \\
 d(x_m, x_n) &\leq b[(\sigma^m + \sigma^{m+1} + \dots + \sigma^{n-1})d(x_0, x_1) + \sum_{i=m}^{n-1} i\sigma^i].
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.21}$$

Since $\sigma^m + \sigma^{m+1} + \dots + \sigma^{n-1}$ is a geometric series with $\sigma < 1$, hence convergent. So, from (3.21), we have

$$d(x_m, x_n) \leq b \left[\frac{\sigma^m}{1 - \sigma} d(x_0, x_1) + \sum_{i=m}^{n-1} i\sigma^i \right]. \tag{3.22}$$

Taking $m, n \rightarrow \infty$ and $\sigma < 1$, the series $\sum_{i=m}^{n-1} i\sigma^i$ converges by Cauchy root test, then

$$d(x_m, x_n) \rightarrow 0. \tag{3.23}$$

Hence existence of Cauchy sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X . Since X is complete, then there exist $x^* \in X$ such that $x_n \rightarrow x^*$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

To show that x^* is an α_L -fuzzy fixed point, we consider

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n+1}, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})] \\
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + H([fx_n]_{\alpha(x_n)}, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})] \\
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b \left[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_1 d(x_n, x^*) + a_2 d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \right. \\
 &\quad + a_3 d(x^*, [fx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_n, [fx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, x^*) + d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, [fx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)})} \\
 &\quad \left. + a_5 \frac{d(x_n, [fx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)}) d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, [fx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, [fx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)})} \right] \\
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b \left[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_1 d(x_n, x^*) + a_2 d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \right. \\
 &\quad + a_3 d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, x^*) + d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \\
 &\quad \left. + a_5 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1}) d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

implies

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b \left[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_1 d(x_n, x^*) + ba_2 d(x_n, x^*) + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. ba_2 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. a_3 d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, x^*) + d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. a_5 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1}) d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1}) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.24}$$

On taking $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.24), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b[ba_2 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})] \\
 (1 - b(ba_2)) d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq 0 \\
 d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.25}$$

Since $(1 - b(ba_2)) \neq 0$. Then $d(x^*, [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) = 0$. Hence $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}$.

Similarly, we consider

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n+1}, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})] \\
 d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) &\leq b[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) \\
 &\quad + H([Tx_n]_{\alpha(x_n)}, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \\
 & \leq b \left[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_1 d(x_n, x^*) + a_2 d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \right. \\
 & + a_3 d(x^*, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_n, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)})d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, x^*) + d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)})} \\
 & \left. + a_5 \frac{d(x_n, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)})d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)})d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, [Tx_n]_{\alpha_L(x_n)})} \right] \\
 & d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \\
 & \leq b \left[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_1 d(x_n, x^*) + a_2 d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \right. \\
 & + a_3 d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1})d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, x^*) + d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \\
 & \left. + a_5 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1})d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

implies

$$\begin{aligned}
 & d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \\
 & \leq b \left[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_1 d(x_n, x^*) + ba_2 d(x_n, x^*) + ba_2 d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \right. \\
 & + a_3 d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + a_4 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1})d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, x^*) + d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \\
 & \left. + a_5 \frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1})d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})}{d(x_n, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) + d(x^*, x_{n+1})} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.26}$$

Taking $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.26), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \leq b[ba_2 d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)})] \\
 & (1 - b(ba_2))d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \leq 0 \\
 & d(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) \leq 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.27}$$

Since $(1 - b(ba_2)) \neq 0$. Hence, $d_{\mathcal{F}}(x^*, [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}) = 0$, which implies $x^* \in [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}$.

Combining the results from (3.25) and (3.27), we have

$$x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)} \cap [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}$$

Thus, T and f have a common α_L -fuzzy fixed point x^* .

Corollary 3.4. Let X be a nonempty set, d be a metric and (X, d) be complete b-metric space with constant $b \geq 1$. Let T be a L-fuzzy mapping from X into $\mathcal{F}_L(X)$ and for all $x, y \in X$, $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i < 1$ with $a_1 + 2ba_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_5 < 1$, there exists $\alpha_L(x), \alpha_L(y) \in (0, 1]$ such that $[Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}$ and $[Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}$ are nonempty and belong to $CB(X)$ satisfying the following requirement:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & H([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) \leq a_1 d(x, y) + a_2 d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + a_3 d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) \\
 & + a_4 \frac{d(x, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, y) + d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})} \\
 & + a_5 \frac{d(x, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.28}$$

Then, T has an α_L -fuzzy fixed point $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_{\mathcal{F}}(x^*)}$.

Proof Let L-fuzzy mappings $A: X \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_L(X)$ be defined as

$$Ax = X_{L_{Tx}}$$

Then, for all $\alpha_L(x) \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$, we get

$$[Ax]_{\alpha_L(x)} = Tx$$

Hence, the remaining part of the proof follows from Theorem 3.1.

Corollary 3.5. Let X be a nonempty set, d be a metric and (X, d) be complete b-metric space with constant $b \geq 1$. Let T be a L-fuzzy mapping from X into $\mathcal{F}_L(X)$ and for all $x, y \in X$, $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6 \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i < 1$ with $a_1 + 2ba_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_5 + a_6 < 1$, there exists $\alpha_L(x), \alpha_L(y) \in (0, 1]$ such that $[Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}$ or $[fx]_{\alpha_L(x)}$ and $[Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}$ or $[fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}$ are nonempty and belong to $CB(X)$ satisfying the following requirement:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & H([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) \leq a_1 d(x, y) + a_2 d(x, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + a_3 d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) \\
 & + a_4 \frac{d(x, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, y) + d(x, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})} \\
 & + a_5 \frac{d(x, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(x, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)})}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.29}$$

Then, T and f have a common α_L -fuzzy fixed point $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)} \cap [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)}$.

Proof Let L-fuzzy mappings $A, B: X \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_L(X)$ be defined as

$$Ax = X_{L_{Tx}}$$

and

$$Bx = X_{L_{fx}}$$

Then, for all $\alpha_L(x) \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$, we get

$$[Ax]_{\alpha_L(x)} = Tx$$

and

$$[Bx]_{\alpha_L(x)} = fx.$$

Hence, the remaining proof follows from Theorem 3.3.

4 Application

Here, we demonstrate applicability of the results developed in the previous sections to derive the existence of α_L -fuzzy fixed point results for multivalued mappings in b-metric spaces. In the sequel, we begin with the following Theorem.

Theorem 4.1 Let X be nonempty set, d be a metric and (X, d) be complete b-metric space with constant $b \geq 1$. Let R be a L-fuzzy mapping from X into $\mathcal{F}_L(X)$ and for all $x, y \in X$, $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i < 1$ with $a_1 + 2ba_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_5 < 1$, there exists $\alpha_L(x), \alpha_L(y) \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$. Suppose R satisfy the following multivalued contraction

$$\begin{aligned}
 & H([Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) \leq a_1 d(x, y) + a_2 d(x, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + a_3 d(y, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) \\
 & + a_4 \frac{d(x, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, y) + d(x, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})} \\
 & + a_5 \frac{d(x, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(x, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

Then, R has an α_L -fuzzy fixed point $x^* \in Rx^*$.

Proof Define L-fuzzy mappings $T: X \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_L(X)$, for some $\alpha_L \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$ by

$$T(x)(t) = \begin{cases} \alpha_L, & \text{if } t \in Rx, \\ 0, & \text{if } t \notin Rx. \end{cases}$$

and

$$T(y)(t) = \begin{cases} \alpha_L, & \text{if } t \in R_2y, \\ 0, & \text{if } t \notin R_2y. \end{cases}$$

Then,

$$[Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)} = Rx,$$

and

$$[Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)} = Ry.$$

Implies for all $x, y \in X$,

$$H_{\mathcal{F}}([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) = H_{\mathcal{F}}(Rx, Ry)$$

The remaining proof follows from Theorem 3.1. Thus $x^* \in X$,

$$x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)} = Rx^*.$$

Theorem 4.2 Let X be nonempty set, d be a metric and (X, d) be complete b-metric space with constant $b \geq 1$. Let R_1, R_2 be a L-fuzzy mapping from X into $\mathcal{F}_L(X)$ and for all $x, y \in X$, $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i < 1$ with $a_1 + 2ba_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_5 < 1$, there exists $\alpha_L(x), \alpha_L(y) \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$. Suppose R_1, R_2 satisfy the following multivalued contraction

$$H([R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) \leq a_1 d(x, y) + a_2 d(x, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + a_3 d(y, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)}) + a_4 \frac{d(x, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, y) + d(x, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})} + a_5 \frac{d(x, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(x, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})} \quad (4.2)$$

Then, R_1, R_2 have a common α_L -fuzzy fixed point $x^* \in R_1x^* \cap R_2x^*$.

Proof Define L-fuzzy mappings $T, f: X \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_L(X)$, for some $\alpha_L \in L \setminus \{0_L\}$ by

$$T(x)(t) = \begin{cases} \alpha_L, & \text{if } t \in R_1x, \\ 0, & \text{if } t \notin R_1x \end{cases}$$

and

$$f(y)(t) = \begin{cases} \alpha_L, & \text{if } t \in R_2y, \\ 0, & \text{if } t \notin R_2y. \end{cases}$$

Then,

$$[Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)} = R_1x$$

and

$$[fy]_{\alpha_L(y)} = R_2y.$$

Implies for all $x, y \in X$,

$$H_{\mathcal{F}}([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}) = H_{\mathcal{F}}(R_1x, R_2y)$$

The remaining proof follows from Theorem 3.3. Thus $x^* \in X$, $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)} \cap [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)} = R_1x^* \cap R_2x^*$.

Theorem 4.3 Let X be nonempty set, d be a metric and (X, d) be complete b-metric space with constant $b \geq 1$. Let R be a L-fuzzy mapping from X into $\mathcal{F}_L(X)$ and for all $x, y \in X$, $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i < 1$ with $a_1 + 2ba_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_5 < 1$, there exists $\alpha_L(x), \alpha_L(y) \in (0, 1]$. Suppose R satisfy the following multivalued contraction

$$H([Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) \leq a_1 d(x, y) + a_2 d(x, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + a_3 d(y, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)}) + a_4 \frac{d(x, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, y) + d(x, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})} + a_5 \frac{d(x, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(x, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, [Ry]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [Rx]_{\alpha_L(x)})} \quad (4.3)$$

Then, R has an α_L -fuzzy fixed point $x^* \in Rx^*$.

Proof Define L-fuzzy mappings $T: X \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_L(X)$, for some $\alpha_L \in (0, 1]$ define by

$$T(x)(t) = \begin{cases} \alpha_L, & \text{if } t \in Rx, \\ 0, & \text{if } t \notin Rx. \end{cases}$$

$$T(y)(t) = \begin{cases} \alpha_L, & \text{if } t \in Ry, \\ 0, & \text{if } t \notin Ry. \end{cases}$$

Then,

$$[Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)} = Rx,$$

and

$$[Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)} = Ry.$$

Implies for all $x, y \in X$,

$$H_{\mathcal{F}}([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [Ty]_{\alpha_L(y)}) = H_{\mathcal{F}}(Rx, Ry)$$

The remaining proof follows from Theorem 3.4. Thus $x^* \in X$, $x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)} = Rx^*$.

Theorem 4.4 Let X be nonempty set, d be a metric and (X, d) be complete b-metric space with constant $b \geq 1$. Let R_1, R_2 be a L-fuzzy mapping from X into $\mathcal{F}_L(X)$ and for all $x, y \in X$, $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^5 a_i < 1$ with $a_1 + 2ba_2 + a_3 +$

$a_4 + a_5 < 1$, there exists $\alpha_L(x), \alpha_L(y) \in (0, 1]$. Suppose R_1, R_2 satisfy the following multivalued contraction

$$H([R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) \leq a_1 d(x, y) + a_2 d(x, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + a_3 d(y, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)}) + a_4 \frac{d(x, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, y) + d(x, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})} + a_5 \frac{d(x, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(x, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})d(y, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)})}{d(x, [R_2y]_{\alpha_L(y)}) + d(y, [R_1x]_{\alpha_L(x)})} \quad (4.4)$$

Then, R_1, R_2 have a common α_L -fuzzy fixed point $x^* \in R_1x^* \cap R_2x^*$.

Proof Define L-fuzzy mappings $T, f: X \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_L(X)$, for some $\alpha_L \in (0, 1]$ define by

$$T(x)(t) = \begin{cases} \alpha_L, & \text{if } t \in R_1x, \\ 0, & \text{if } t \notin R_1x \end{cases}$$

and

$$f(y)(t) = \begin{cases} \alpha_L, & \text{if } t \in R_2y, \\ 0, & \text{if } t \notin R_2y. \end{cases}$$

Then,

$$[Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)} = R_1x$$

and

$$[fy]_{\alpha_L(y)} = R_2y.$$

Implies for all $x, y \in X$,

$$H_{\mathcal{F}}([Tx]_{\alpha_L(x)}, [fy]_{\alpha_L(y)}) = H_{\mathcal{F}}(R_1x, R_2y)$$

The remaining proof follows from Theorem 3.5. Thus $x^* \in X$,

$$x^* \in [Tx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)} \cap [fx^*]_{\alpha_L(x^*)} = R_1x^* \cap R_2x^*.$$

4. Conclusions

The main findings of this study demonstrated applicability of L-fuzzy mapping and established α_L -fuzzy fixed point results for rational contraction within the complete b-metric spaces. This study provides significant advancements in the understanding of L-fuzzy mapping, through illustrative examples, we showcased the practical applicability of the results and explored as an application, the solution for fuzzy contraction to derive the existence of α_L -fuzzy fixed point results for multivalued mappings in b-metric spaces. Future work could also explore the extension of this results to other types of fuzzy mappings.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The authors declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The author declared that there are no competing interests.

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